

Molecular biology, expression and clinical significance of ErbB receptors in endometrial cancer

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Abstract

The epidermal growth factor system (EGF system) is present in human organs and play important role in cell proliferation, differentiation and apoptosis during embryogenesis and postnatal development. It has 4 receptors (EGFR, ErbB - 2, ErbB - 3 and ErbB - 4) and numerous ligands. Dysregulation of the epidermal growth factor system signaling network, is implicated in the pathogenesis of various disorders. Especially in cancer, the epidermal growth factor system becomes hyperactivated with various mechanisms (ligand overproduction, receptor overproduction, constitutive receptor activation). Endometrial cancer occurs primarily in postmenopausal women. Due to the inactive status of postmenopausal endometrium, it is expectable to find significantly higher expression of the 4 ErbB receptors in endometrial cancer tissue. EGFR overexpression in type I endome-

trial cancer, did not affect disease progression. However EGFR overexpression in type II endometrial cancer, associated with high grade and adverse clinical outcome. Moreover ErbB - 2 overexpression, especially in type II endometrial cancer, is an indicator of a highly aggressive disease with poor overall survival. The clinical significance of ErbB receptors in endometrial cancer should be further investigated in future clinical trials. Moreover additional studies into the molecular pathways of endometrial cancer development and progression, will increase our knowledge and lead to the discovery of new generation molecules with higher therapeutic efficacy.

Key words: endometrial cancer; epidermal growth factor system; ErbB receptors; molecular biology; expression; clinical significance

The epidermal growth factor system (EGF system) is present in human organs and play important role in cell proliferation, differentiation and apoptosis during embryogenesis and postnatal development¹⁻³.

Dysregulation of the EGF signaling network is implicated in various disorders¹⁻⁴. Especially in cancer, the EGF system contributes in proliferation, transformation, angiogenesis, migration and invasion^{2,3,5}.

Endometrial cancer (EC) is the most common ma-

lignancy of the female genital tract and occurs primarily in postmenopausal women⁶. Due to the inactive status of postmenopausal endometrium, it is expectable to find significantly higher expression of the EGF system in EC tissue^{2,3,7}.

Molecular biology of the EGF system Receptors and ligands

The EGF system is present in human organs and

play important role during embryogenesis and postnatal development¹⁻³.

The EGF system has 4 receptors: epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) (also known as ErbB - 1, HER1), ErbB - 2 (also known as HER2, Neu), ErbB - 3 (also known as HER3) and ErbB - 4 (also known as HER4)^{1,3,5,8}.

ErbB receptors belong to subclass I of the superfamily of Receptor Tyrosine Kinases (RTKs)^{1,5}. They are trans - membrane glycoproteins with an extracellular region containing two ligand - binding domains, an extracellular juxtamembrane region, a hydrophobic transmembrane domain and an intracellular domain with tyrosine kinase activity^{8,9}. They catalyze the transfer of the γ phosphate of ATP to hydroxyl groups of tyrosines in target proteins⁹.

Moreover, EGF system has numerous ligands^{2,3,8}. According to their affinity for one or more ErbB receptors, they are divided into three groups:

Ligands with binding specificity for EGFR: EGF, transforming growth factor - α (TGF - α) and amphiregulin (AR)^{5,8}.

Ligands with dual binding specificity for EGFR and ErbB4: betacellulin (BTC), heparin-binding growth factor (HB - EGF) and epiregulin (EPR)^{5,8}.

Ligands with binding specificity for ErbB - 3 and ErbB - 4: neuregulins (NRGs) or heregulins (HRGs). They are divided in two subgroups based on their ability to bind ErbB - 3 and ErbB - 4 (NRG - 1 and NRG - 2) or only ErbB - 4 (NRG-3 and NRG - 4)^{5,8}.

Receptors activation

The extracellular region of EGFR, ErbB - 3 and ErbB - 4 has two distinct conformations:

Closed conformation (inactive) which has intramolecular interactions between subdomains II and IV^{9,10}.

Open conformation (active), where subdomains I and III form a ligand - binding pocket that permits interactions between a single ligand and subdomains I and III^{9,10}.

In the absence of ligand binding, the extracellular region of EGFR, ErbB - 3 and ErbB - 4 has equilibri-

um between closed and open conformation⁹⁻¹¹. This equilibrium favours the closed conformation⁹⁻¹¹.

Ligand binding stabilizes extracellular region in the open conformation and leads to the formation of both homodimeric and heterodimeric ErbB receptor complexes⁹⁻¹². The dimeric formation triggers receptor activation by an allosteric mechanism^{10,12} which leads to intracellular kinase activation and initiation of downstream signaling pathways^{8,12}.

The extracellular region of ErbB - 2 has a conformation not suitable for ligand binding¹³. However, this conformation allows extension of the receptor dimerization arm in subdomain II^{9,13}. This suggests that ErbB - 2 is capable for ligand independent dimerization and signaling⁹. ErbB - 2 heterodimerizes with other ErbB receptors and it is their preferred heterodimerization partner^{8,12,13}. At elevated expression levels ErbB - 2 homodimerizes¹³.

ErbB - 3 lacks intrinsic tyrosine kinase activity and therefore can initiate signaling only in association with another ErbB receptor, usually ErbB - 2^{2,3,8}. ErbB - 2 and ErbB - 3 heterodimer is the most transforming and mitogenic receptor complex and increases cell motility on stimulation with a ligand⁸.

The dimerization of ErbB receptors represents the fundamental mechanism that drives transformation^{2,3,8}.

Signaling pathways

Dimerization of ErbB receptors leads to intracellular kinase activation^{8,12}. Subsequently, a number of tyrosine residues in the COOH - terminal portion of ErbB receptors become phosphorylated^{5,13}. These phosphorylated tyrosine residues function as docking sites for cytoplasmic proteins containing Src homology 2 (SH2) and phosphotyrosine binding (PTB) domains^{4,8}. Recruitment of proteins initiates intracellular signaling via several pathways:

Ras / Raf / mitogen - activated protein kinase (MAPK) pathway

The Ras / Raf / mitogen - activated protein kinase (MAPK) pathway regulates cell proliferation and

survival¹⁴. Following ErbB phosphorylation, the complex of Grb2 and Sos adaptor proteins binds directly or indirectly (through Shc adaptor protein) to specific intracellular ErbB docking sites¹⁴.

This interaction results in conformational modification of Sos, leading to recruitment of Ras - GDP and subsequent Ras activation (Ras - GTP)¹⁵. Ras-GTP activates Raf - 1 and, through intermediate steps, phosphorylates MAPK - 1 and MAPK - 2¹⁵. Activated MAPKs phosphorylate and regulate specific intranuclear transcription factors involved in cell migration and proliferation¹⁴.

Phosphatidylinositol 3 - kinase (PI3K)/Akt pathway

The Phosphatidylinositol 3 - kinase (PI3K)/ Akt pathway regulates cell growth, apoptosis, tumor invasion, migration and resistance to chemotherapy¹⁶.

PI3K is a dimeric enzyme that composed of a regulatory p85 subunit and a catalytic p110 subunit¹⁶. The regulatory p85 subunit, is responsible of the anchorage to ErbB receptor specific docking sites, through interaction of its Src homology domain 2 (SH2) with phosphotyrosine residues¹⁶. The catalytic p110 subunit, catalyzes the phosphorylation of phosphatidylinositol 4, 5 diphosphate at the 3' position¹⁶. Phosphatidylinositol 3, 4, 5 triphosphate, phosphorylates and activates the protein serine/threonine kinase Akt¹⁶.

ErbB receptor specific docking sites for p85 subunit are present on ErbB - 3 and absent on EGFR⁸. EGFR dependent PI3K activation occurs through dimerization of EGFR with ErbB - 3 or through the docking protein Gab - 1¹⁴.

Signal transducers and activators of transcription (STAT) pathway

Signal transducers and activators of transcription (STAT) pathway regulates oncogenesis and tumor progression¹⁷.

STAT proteins interact with phosphotyrosine residues via their Src homology domain 2 (SH2) and, on dimerization, translocate to the nucleus and induce the expression of specific target genes¹⁸.

Constitutive activation of STAT proteins (especially STAT - 3 and STAT - 5) is present in various primary cancers^{17,18}.

EGFR regulate STAT pathway through a Janus kinase (JAK) or a JAK independent mechanism¹⁷. Augmented activity of EGFR and ErbB - 2, promotes persistent STAT - 3 activation and subsequently induces oncogenesis and tumor progression¹⁷.

Src Kinase pathway

The Src kinase pathway regulates cell proliferation, migration, adhesion, angiogenesis, and immune function¹⁹.

Src is a member of a 10 genes family (FYN, YES, BLK, FRK, FGR, HCK, LCK, LYN, SRMS) of non - RTKs. It is located in the cytoplasm and cross - connected with other signaling pathways, such as PI3K and STAT pathway¹⁹.

Although Src functions independently, it may interact with RTKs such as EGFR. The interaction between Src and EGFR may enhance ErbB signaling and may be involved in resistance to EGFR targeted therapy¹³.

Phospholipase C γ / protein kinase C pathway

Phospholipase C γ (PLC γ) interacts directly with activated EGFR and ErbB - 2 and hydrolyses phosphatidylinositol 4, 5 diphosphate to inositol 1, 3, 5 triphosphate (IP3) and 1, 2 diacylglycerol (DAG)²⁰.

IP3 is important for intracellular calcium release. DAG is cofactor in protein kinase C (PKC) activation. Activated PKC activates MAPK and c - Jun NH2 - terminal kinase²¹.

Dysregulation and carcinogenesis

Dysregulation of the EGF system signaling network is implicated in cancer, diabetes, autoimmune, in inflammatory, cardiovascular and nervous system disorders^{1,4}.

Loss of control of the cell functions mediated by the EGF system signaling network is a hallmark in oncogenesis^{2,3}. Several types of human cancers are associated with dysregulation of the EGF system signaling network¹.

Especially in cancer, the EGF system signaling network becomes hyperactivated with a range of mechanisms (ligand overproduction, receptor overproduction, constitutive receptor activation)^{2,4,8}. It also contributes in proliferation, transformation, angiogenesis, migration and invasion⁵.

Expression of ErbB receptors in endometrial cancer

EC is the most common malignancy of the female genital tract and occurs primarily in postmenopausal women⁶. Overall, 2.64% of women develop EC during their lifetime⁶. Based on clinical and pathological features, sporadic EC is classified into 2 types^{22,23}.

Type I EC, represents the majority of sporadic EC cases (70 - 80%)^{22,23}. It is usually well differentiated and endometrioid in histology^{22,23}. It is estrogen - related and usually arises from endometrial hyperplasia^{22,23}. It has less aggressive clinical course and favorable prognosis^{22,23}.

Type II EC, represents the minority of sporadic EC cases (10 - 20%)^{22,23}. It is poorly differentiated and usually papillary serous or clear cell in histology^{22,23}. It is not estrogen - related and arises from atrophic endometrium²². It has aggressive clinical course and propensity for early spread and poor prognosis²².

Due to the inactive status of postmenopausal endometrium, it is expectable to find significantly higher expression of the 4 ErbB receptors in EC tissue^{2,3,7}.

EGFR localized to the basal part of surface epithelial cells, only in stromal cells, or both to epithelial and stromal cells of endometrium^{2,3,24-27}. It is primarily located to the cell membrane but also located to the cytoplasm^{2,3,7,25-29}.

In unselected patients with EC, it has been reported EGFR expression in 43 - 67% of cases^{2,3,25,26,28,31}. In patients with type I EC, it has been reported EGFR expression in 46% of cases^{2,3}. In patients with type II EC, it has been reported EGFR expression in 34 - 50% of cases^{2,3,27,30,32}.

ErbB-2 is localized baso - laterally in the glands and surface epithelial cells of endometrium^{2,3,24-27}. It is located to the cell membrane^{2,3,7,25-29,33}.

In unselected patients with EC, ErbB - 2 amplifica-

tion/overexpression represents a rare event³¹. In patients with type I EC, it has been reported ErbB - 2 receptor overexpression in 8% of cases and ErbB - 2 gene amplification in 1.4 - 3% of cases^{30,34}. Although ErbB - 2 amplification/overexpression is more common in patients with type II EC, the exact frequency remains controversial^{2,3,27,30}. Moreover, there are racial differences regarding ErbB - 2 overexpression in patients with type II EC^{3,35}. ErbB - 2 overexpression is more common in Black race patients with type II EC³⁵.

In patients with papillary serous EC, it has been reported ErbB - 2 receptor overexpression in 18% - 80% of cases and ErbB - 2 gene amplification in 17 - 47% of cases^{2,3,27,30,34,36}. In patients with clear cell EC, it has been reported ErbB - 2 receptor overexpression in 33% of cases and ErbB - 2 gene amplification in 16 - 50% of cases^{2,3,27,30,34,36}.

ErbB - 3 is localized to surface epithelial cells of endometrium^{2,3,24-27,37}. It is located in the cytoplasm, with membrane staining in a minority of samples^{2,3,7,25-27,37}.

ErbB - 4 is localized at epithelial and stromal cells of endometrium^{2,3,24-27,37}. It is located in the cytoplasm, with membrane staining in a minority of samples^{2,3,7,25-27,37}.

Clinical significance of ErbB receptors in endometrial cancer

Overexpression and structural alterations of EGFR in various cancers are associated with higher grade, disease progression, poor survival and resistance to radiotherapy and chemotherapy⁸. Although the clinical significance of EGFR has not been studied well in EC, it may have a dual role^{2,3,30}. EGFR overexpression did not affect disease progression in type I EC, although affects disease progression in type II EC³⁰. EGFR overexpression in type II EC is associated with high grade disease and adverse clinical outcome^{2,3,27,30,32}.

Overexpression of ErbB - 2 in various cancers is an indicator of a more aggressive clinical behavior^{8,33}. ErbB-2 overexpression especially in type II EC, is an indicator of a highly aggressive disease with poor overall survival^{2,3,27,32-34,38}.

Overexpression of ErbB - 3 in various cancers is related with ErbB - 2 positivity and lymph node involvement^{39,40}. However, a definitive relationship with survival has not been established^{39,40}. The clinical significance of ErbB-3 has not been studied well in EC^{2,3,7,25-27,32,37}.

Overexpression of ErbB - 4 is related with favorable prognosis in breast and bladder cancer⁴¹. The clinical significance of ErbB - 4 has not been studied well in EC^{2,3,7, 25-27,32,37}.

It is obvious that the clinical significance of ErbB receptors in EC should be further investigated in future clinical trials^{2,3,27, 30,33,42-47}. Moreover, additional studies into the molecular pathways of EC development and progression, will increase our knowledge and lead to the discovery of new generation molecules with higher therapeutic efficacy^{2,3,27}. ■

Conflict of interest

All authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

1. Uberall I, Kolar Z, Trojanec R, Berkovcova J, Hajduch M. The status and role of ErbB receptors in human cancer. *Exp Mol Pathol* 2008;84:79 - 89.
2. Adonakis G, Androutsopoulos G. The role of ErbB receptors in endometrial cancer. In: Saldivar JS, Editor. *Cancer of the uterine endometrium - advances and controversies*. InTech, 2012, p. 23 - 38.
3. Androutsopoulos G, Adonakis G, Decavalas G. ErbB targeted therapy in endometrial cancer. In: Farghaly SA, Editor. *Endometrial cancer: current epidemiology, detection and management*: Nova Science Publishers, 2014.
4. Marmor M, Skaria K, Yarden Y. Signal transduction and oncogenesis by ErbB/HER receptors. *Int J Radiat Oncol Biol Phys* 2004;58:903 - 13.
5. Holbro T, Civenni G, Hynes N. The ErbB receptors and their role in cancer progression. *Exp Cell Res* 2003;284: 99 - 110.
6. Siegel R, Naishadham D, Jemal A. Cancer statistics, 2013. *CA Cancer J Clin* 2013;63:11 - 30.
7. Ejskjaer K, Sorensen BS, Poulsen SS, Forman A, Nexø E, Mogensen O. Expression of the epidermal growth factor system in endometrioid endometrial cancer. *Gynecol Oncol* 2007;104:158 - 67.
8. Yarden Y. The EGFR family and its ligands in human cancer. signalling mechanisms and therapeutic opportunities. *Eur J Cancer* 2001;37 Suppl 4:S3 - 8.
9. Riese D, Gallo R, Settleman J. Mutational activation of ErbB family receptor tyrosine kinases: insights into mechanisms of signal transduction and tumorigenesis. *Bioessays* 2007;29:558 - 65.
10. Dawson J, Berger M, Lin C, Schlessinger J, Lemmon M, Ferguson K. Epidermal growth factor receptor dimerization and activation require ligand-induced conformational changes in the dimer interface. *Mol Cell Biol* 2005;25:7734 - 42.
11. Ozcan F, Klein P, Lemmon M, Lax I, Schlessinger J. On the nature of low - and high - affinity EGF receptors on living cells. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 2006;103:5735 - 40.
12. Olayioye M, Neve R, Lane H, Hynes N. The ErbB signaling network: receptor heterodimerization in development and cancer. *EMBO J* 2000;19: 3159 - 67.
13. Jorissen R, Walker F, Pouliot N, Garrett T, Ward C, Burgess A. Epidermal growth factor receptor: mechanisms of activation and signalling. *Exp Cell Res* 2003;284:31 - 53.
14. Scaltriti M, Baselga J. The epidermal growth factor receptor pathway: a model for targeted therapy. *Clin Cancer Res* 2006;12:5268 - 72.
15. Hallberg B, Rayter S, Downward J. Interaction of Ras and Raf in intact mammalian cells upon extracellular stimulation. *J Biol Chem* 1994;269:3913 - 6.
16. Vivanco I, Sawyers C. The phosphatidylinositol 3-Kinase AKT pathway in human cancer. *Nat Rev Cancer* 2002;2:489 - 501.
17. Bromberg J. Stat proteins and oncogenesis. *J Clin Invest* 2002;109:1139 - 42.
18. Haura E, Turkson J, Jove R. Mechanisms of disease: Insights into the emerging role of signal transducers and activators of transcription in cancer. *Nat Clin Pract Oncol* 2005;2:315 - 24.
19. Yeatman T. A renaissance for SRC. *Nat Rev Cancer* 2004;4:470 - 80.
20. Chattopadhyay A, Vecchi M, Ji Q, Mernaugh R, Carpenter G. The role of individual SH2 domains in

- mediating association of phospholipase C-gamma1 with the activated EGF receptor. *J Biol Chem* 1999;274:26091 - 7.
21. Schonwasser D, Marais R, Marshall C, Parker P. Activation of the mitogen - activated protein kinase/ extracellular signal - regulated kinase pathway by conventional, novel, and atypical protein kinase C isotypes. *Mol Cell Biol* 1998;18:790 - 8.
 22. Bokhman J. Two pathogenetic types of endometrial carcinoma. *Gynecol Oncol* 1983;15:10 - 7.
 23. Doll A, Abal M, Rigau M, et al. Novel molecular profiles of endometrial cancer - new light through old windows. *J Steroid Biochem Mol Biol* 2008;108:221 - 29.
 24. Ejskjaer K, Sorensen BS, Poulsen SS, Mogensen O, Forman A, Nexø E. Expression of the epidermal growth factor system in human endometrium during the menstrual cycle. *Mol Hum Reprod* 2005;11:543 - 51.
 25. Androutsopoulos G, Adonakis G, Gkermepesi M, Gkogkos P, Ravazoula P, Kourounis G. Expression of the epidermal growth factor system in endometrial cancer after adjuvant tamoxifen treatment for breast cancer. *Eur J Gynaecol Oncol* 2006;27:490 - 4.
 26. Adonakis G, Androutsopoulos G, Koumoundourou D, Liava A, Ravazoula P, Kourounis G. Expression of the epidermal growth factor system in endometrial cancer. *Eur J Gynaecol Oncol* 2008;29:450 - 4.
 27. Androutsopoulos G, Adonakis G, Liava A, Ravazoula P, Decavalas G. Expression and potential role of ErbB receptors in type II endometrial cancer. *Eur J Obstet Gynecol Reprod Biol* 2013;168:204 - 08.
 28. Reinartz J, George E, Lindgren B, Niehans G. Expression of p53, transforming growth factor alpha, epidermal growth factor receptor, and c-erbB-2 in endometrial carcinoma and correlation with survival and known predictors of survival. *Hum Pathol* 1994;25:1075 - 83.
 29. Khalifa MA, Mannel RS, Haraway SD, Walker J, Min KW. Expression of EGFR, HER-2/neu, P53, and PCNA in endometrioid, serous papillary, and clear cell endometrial adenocarcinomas. *Gynecol Oncol* 1994;53:84 - 92.
 30. Konecny G, Santos L, Winterhoff B, et al. HER2 gene amplification and EGFR expression in a large cohort of surgically staged patients with nonendometrioid (type II) endometrial cancer. *Br J Cancer* 2009;100:89 - 95.
 31. Brys M, Semczuk A, Rechberger T, Krajewska W. Expression of erbB-1 and erbB-2 genes in normal and pathological human endometrium. *Oncol Rep* 2007;18:261 - 5.
 32. Androutsopoulos G, Michail G, Adonakis G, Decavalas G. ErbB receptors and ErbB targeted therapies in endometrial cancer. *J Cancer Ther* 2014;5:483 - 92.
 33. Odicino F, Bignotti E, Rossi E, et al. HER-2/neu overexpression and amplification in uterine serous papillary carcinoma: comparative analysis of immunohistochemistry, real-time reverse transcription - polymerase chain reaction, and fluorescence in situ hybridization. *Int J Gynecol Cancer* 2008;18:14 - 21.
 34. Morrison C, Zanagnolo V, Ramirez N, et al. HER-2 is an independent prognostic factor in endometrial cancer: association with outcome in a large cohort of surgically staged patients. *J Clin Oncol* 2006;24(15):2376 - 85.
 35. Santin A, Bellone S, Siegel E, et al. Racial differences in the overexpression of epidermal growth factor type II receptor (HER2/neu): a major prognostic indicator in uterine serous papillary cancer. *Am J Obstet Gynecol* 2005;192:813 - 8.
 36. Grushko T, Filiaci V, Mundt A, Ridderstrale K, Olopade O, Fleming G. An exploratory analysis of HER-2 amplification and overexpression in advanced endometrial carcinoma: a Gynecologic Oncology Group study. *Gynecol Oncol* 2008;108:3 - 9.
 37. Srinivasan R, Benton E, McCormick F, Thomas H, Gullick W. Expression of the c-erbB-3/HER-3 and c-erbB-4/HER-4 growth factor receptors and their ligands, neuregulin-1 alpha, neuregulin-1 beta, and betacellulin, in normal endometrium and endometrial cancer. *Clin Cancer Res* 1999;5:2877 - 83.
 38. Santin A, Bellone S, Van Stedum S, et al. Amplification of c-erbB2 oncogene: a major prognostic indicator in uterine serous papillary carcinoma. *Cancer* 2005;104:1391 - 7.
 39. Gasparini G, Gullick W, Maluta S, et al. c-erbB-3 and

- c-erbB-2 protein expression in node - negative breast carcinoma - an immunocytochemical study. *Eur J Cancer* 1994;30A:16 - 22.
40. Bieche I, Onody P, Tozlu S, Driouch K, Vidaud M, Lidereau R. Prognostic value of ERBB family mRNA expression in breast carcinomas. *Int J Cancer* 2003;106:758 - 65.
 41. Suo Z, Risberg B, Kallsson M, et al. EGFR family expression in breast carcinomas. c-erbB-2 and c-erbB-4 receptors have different effects on survival. *J Pathol* 2002;196:17 - 25.
 42. Santin A, Bellone S, Roman J, McKenney J, Pecorelli S. Trastuzumab treatment in patients with advanced or recurrent endometrial carcinoma overexpressing HER2/neu. *Int J Gynaecol Obstet* 2008;102:128 -31.
 43. Oza A, Eisenhauer E, Elit L, et al. Phase II study of erlotinib in recurrent or metastatic endometrial cancer: NCIC IND-148. *J Clin Oncol* 2008;26: 4319 - 25.
 44. Fleming G, Sill M, Darcy K, et al. Phase II trial of trastuzumab in women with advanced or recurrent, HER2-positive endometrial carcinoma: a Gynecologic Oncology Group study. *Gynecol Oncol* 2010;116:15 - 20.
 45. Roque D, Santin A. Updates in therapy for uterine serous carcinoma. *Curr Opin Obstet Gynecol* 2013;25:29 - 37.
 46. Androutsopoulos G. Current treatment options in patients with endometrial cancer. *J Community Med Health Educ* 2012;2: e113.
 47. Androutsopoulos G, Decavalas G. Management of endometrial cancer. *Int J Transl Comm Med* 2013;1:101.